

THE EFFECT OF FATIGUE DAMAGE ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CFRP COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A study has been made of the fatigue response of two high-performance CFRP laminates, XAS/914 and T800/5245. The residual strengths and stiffnesses of the materials have been established as a function of the number of fatigue cycles sustained at stress levels between 60 and 90% of their monotonic tensile strengths, and edge replication has been used to investigate the points of onset of the various damage mechanisms which contribute to this deterioration in properties. When the differences in strength of the two materials are taken into account, it appears that the older XAS system exhibits the superior fatigue resistance.

1 INTRODUCTION

The cyclic loading of composite materials introduces damage by a variety of mechanisms. The damage mechanisms with which we are most familiar are resin cracking, fibre fracture, fibre/matrix debonding, and delamination, but the predominance of any particular mechanism, the sequence in which the mechanisms occur, and possibly the extent to which they interact are likely to vary with the constituents of the composite, the nature of the interface, the laminate lay-up and its quality, and the environmental conditions. The consequence of the accumulation of damage that occurs during fatigue is generally a deterioration in the important mechanical properties of the composite, namely the elastic stiffness, the strength and the toughness. Attempts have been made to use the changes in stiffness as an indicator of the degree of fatigue damage incurred^(1,2) and measurements of residual strength as a means of predicting fatigue life⁽³⁾. In a recent paper⁽⁴⁾ we reported some early results from this program showing that

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repeated tension cycling of a $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ CFRP laminate resulted in changes in both the notched and the un-notched tensile strengths in such a fashion that there was a relatively small net change in the ratio K_{IC}/σ_f , the fracture toughness divided by the tensile strength, even after 10^4 to 10^5 cycles at stresses as high as 80% of the undamaged tensile failure stress. In this paper we present a more detailed comparison of the responses of two high-performance laminates to repeated tension cycling, presenting information on the accumulation of damage in the form of damage maps. The objective of this work is to develop a more realistic structure/property-based fatigue life prediction model.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The materials studied were laminates of the two CFRP systems XAS/914, manufactured by Ciba-Geigy, and T800/5245, produced by BASF. The former is a well-established aerospace system based on BSL914 resin, a mixed tetra- and tri-functional system related to the Ciba MY720 resin, while the latter is a more recently developed system based on Toray intermediate modulus T800H carbon fibre in a Narmco 5245 resin. This resin is described by the manufacturer as an epoxy/bismaleimide. The laminates were hot pressed from prepreg materials according to the manufacturers' instructions. No detailed information regarding the preparation of the prepreps and the fibres in them is available, but it was apparent from the appearances of fracture surfaces that the level of adhesion in the T800/5245 material was markedly inferior to that in the older XAS/914 laminate.

Results have been obtained for both systems in a $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ layup, a structure of interest for aircraft wing structures, and for comparison purposes a certain amount of work has also been carried out on unidirectional composites of the XAS/914 system. The basic tensile properties of these experimental materials are shown in table 1.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of experimental laminates.

System	Layup	Tensile modulus GPa	Tensile strength GPa	Failure strain %
XAS/914	$(0)_8$	122±11	1.6±0.1	1.2±0.1
XAS/914	$[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$	80±4	1.0±0.1	1.3±0.1
T800/5245	$[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$	90±4	1.6±0.1	1.7±0.1

A series of experiments was carried out to evaluate systematically the fatigue damage mechanisms that occur at different cyclic stress levels during repeated tension loading

($R = +0.1$) to peak stress levels between about 60% and 90% of the tensile strength. They were carried out in Instron 1300 series servo-hydraulic test machines controlled by Macintosh computers via SarGen control and data acquisition units built by Marandy Instruments of Bath. All fatigue tests were carried out at between 5 and 10Hz at a stress ratio, $R = \sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max}$, of +0.1. The variation in dynamic stiffness was continuously monitored during cycling, and tests were halted at intervals to permit the evaluation of the damage state in the composite by edge replication. A second set of experiments involved the fatiguing of samples to predetermined numbers of cycles, following which the residual tensile stiffness and strength, and, in the case of the $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ XAS/914 material, the notched tensile strength, were measured.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fatigue Response

The stress/log life curves for the three composites are presented in figure 1. These are smoothed curves with experimental points omitted for the sake of clarity. The three curves are similar in that they are reasonably linear over the first four or five decades and show slight evidence of a gradual downturn at long lives.

Figure 1. Stress/loglife curves for $(0)_8$ and $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ XAS/914 and $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ T800/5245 laminate for repeated tension cycling.

The effect of cycling to peak stress levels between about 60% and 90% of the tensile failure strength, σ_f , on the residual strength and stiffness of the composites, normalized with respect to the undamaged values in each case, is shown in figures 2 to 4. The stiffnesses of the two $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ laminates vary in similar fashion, with a slight initial increase (of the order of a few percent only) in the region of about one thousand cycles followed by a gradual reduction which appears not to be very sensitive to the cyclic stress level. The two sets of data overlap substantially in these normalized plots despite the difference in actual laminate properties. The unidirectional composite is clearly less susceptible to damage: the data points for the 90% σ_f stress level overlap with those for all stress levels for the $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ materials, but at lower cycling stresses the residual stiffness remains unaffected, apart, again, from a slight increase, until well beyond 10^5 cycles. We note that the dynamic stiffness monitored continuously during fatigue tests to destruction shows the same variation with number of cycles as the residual stiffness.

Figure 2. Residual modulus, strength and notched strength of fatigued samples of $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ XAS/914 laminate cycled at various stress levels. Symbols identify fatigue stress levels as % of tensile strength, and the residual properties are normalized with respect to undamaged values.

Figure 3. Residual modulus and strength of fatigued samples of $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_s$ T800/5245 laminate cycled at various stress levels.

Figure 4. Residual modulus and strength of fatigued samples of unidirectional $(0)_s$ XAS/914 laminate cycled at various stress levels.

The un-notched strength changes show some similarities, including the slight increase in strength before the inevitable subsequent reduction. For the two XAS/914 laminates the data points are reasonably close except for the cycling at $90\%\sigma_f$ which affects the unidirectional composite more markedly than cycling at $93\%\sigma_f$ affects the laminate with 45° plies. The most significant difference here, however, is for the $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ T800/5245 laminate and it can be seen from figure 4 that the residual strength of this material begins to fall after only 100 or so cycles even at the lowest cycling stress used, $61\%\sigma_f$.

The residual notched strength has only been determined for the $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ XAS/914 laminate. From figure 2 it is seen to show the same general features as the variations in un-notched strength with the difference that it starts to fall sooner than the un-notched strength and suggests a greater sensitivity to the actual cyclic stress level as shown by the data points for $90\%\sigma_f$.

3.2 Damage Observations

The edge replication technique provides information about the damage state of a sample without necessitating its removal from the fatigue machine. Reliance on the method naturally involves the assumption that damage observed on an external edge also reflects the true state of damage in the bulk of the solid. The observations reported here have in fact been backed by supporting experiments in which we have taken successive longitudinal slices through the sample and compared the appearance of damage on the cut and polished faces with that in the edge replicas. This has shown that the edge replication information was indeed characteristic of the bulk damaged state.

In the $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ XAS/914 laminate, the first damage to occur was matrix cracking in the least constrained, outer 45° plies, and this was followed very closely by the first observations of fibre damage in the load-bearing 0° plies. After a longer interval, matrix cracks were observed in the inner 45° plies. Longitudinal cracks, or splits, are less easy to observe by edge replication since, unlike transverse (or angle) cracks there is no tendency for them to be held open. But the effect of longitudinal cracking is easily observed, since it leads to separation of fibres from the matrix through debonding, and, where the fibres are themselves already suffering breakage, to their release from the composite. This is observed in the edge replicas as the dropping out of small lengths of fibre. The same phenomenon could also be seen in cut and polished sections. Only after this sequence of damage events do we see any evidence of delamination. This is observed, first, as delamination between pairs of 45° plies, where the

interlaminar shear stresses are greatest, and subsequently delaminations are observed between 0° and 45° plies.

Figure 5. Schematic maps of fatigue damage mechanisms for ud and $[(\pm 45, 0)_2]_s$ XAS/914 laminates; stress ratio, $R = +0.1$.

The replica information may be presented in the form of a damage mechanisms map, as in figures 5 and 6 which also include the $S/\log N$ curves. The lower section of figure 5 presents the results for the $[(\pm 45, 0)_2]_s$ XAS composite. At the higher cyclic stresses the range over which the individual damage mechanisms occur is very wide (3 decades at $90\% \sigma_f$, for example) but that in this logarithmic presentation the curves tend to bunch together more the lower the cyclic stress. It is interesting to note that the same group of mechanisms occurs whatever the stress level, even when that stress is too low for us to obtain an actual fatigue failure in a reasonable amount of time.

The damage map for the T800 $[(\pm 45, 0)_2]_s$ composite is quite different from that for the XAS material, as figure 6 shows. Instead of bunching together at the lower stresses, the curves fan out, the first damage for the lowest cyclic stress appearing after less than 100. The sequence of damage mechanisms is also different, the first visible damage being fibre breakage in the 0° plies which now occurs before any matrix cracking. Since in the two $[(\pm 45, 0)_2]_s$ composites the fibres should, in principle, be working only over the same range of stresses, relative to their tensile strengths, it might be thought that the marked difference in the point of onset of fibre damage in the two composites would be due to the difference in matrix

flexibility/toughness, But we also see, unexpectedly, that the first matrix cracking also occurs earlier in the T800 laminate, which runs counter to the proposed effect of resin flexibility. Fibre drop out, which requires fibre/matrix separation after the occurrence of fibre breakage, also occurs earlier in the T800 composite. In this case it seems certain that this is a reflexion of our earlier observation that bonding in the T800 composite is poorer than in the XAS/914 system.

Figure 6. Schematic maps of fatigue damage mechanisms for $[(\pm 45, 0)_2]_s$ T800/5245 laminates; stress ratio, $R = +0.1$.

The much simpler damage map for the unidirectional XAS/914 laminate is shown in the upper half of figure 5. Only two of the mechanisms observed in the other two laminates occurred in this material prior to failure, namely fibre fracture and fibre drop out, since no off-axis plies are present. In this case, however, there is much closer correspondence between the two damage curves (labelled 2 and 4 in figure 5) and the curves for the equivalent mechanisms in the T800 composite (curves 1 and 3 in figure 6) rather than with the equivalent curves in the XAS/914 $[(\pm 45, 0)_2]_s$ laminate. That is to say that both fibre fracture and fibre drop out occur earlier in the unidirectional composite than in the $[(\pm 45, 0)_2]_s$ version of the same system. This comparison appears to suggest that the presence of the 45° plies exerts a beneficial effect on the fatigue response of the XAS/914 system by delaying the onset of various damage events. The inference is that the same is not true of the 45° plies in the T800 composite.

Comparison between the residual properties results and the damage maps suggests that fibre fracture and matrix cracking in the 45° plies do not much affect the basic tensile properties of

the composites studied, and that it is only when the combination of events that leads to fibre drop out begins to occur that marked strength reductions are seen. Subsequent delamination damage in the $[(\pm 45, 0_2)_2]_S$ composites further reduces the load-bearing ability of the material.

The shapes of the damage mechanism curves can, of course, only be determined to within a limited degree of accuracy unless the fatigue tests are stopped at inconveniently short intervals. Nevertheless, the shapes of the curves and their relationship with the established parts of the material $S/\log N$ curve suggest that although the latter cannot be fully determined in a reasonable experimental time scale, their shapes will probably resemble that of the family of damage curves, and we have begun to use this concept to develop a life prediction model⁽⁵⁾.

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